

FORMING MOTIVATION IN STUDENTS OF MILITARY EDUCATION.

Nazarov Tohir Toshpulatovich

Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute
Associate Professor of Special Training Cycle,
Faculty of Military Education.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15173601>

Annotation: The content of relationships is of great importance in strengthening military discipline in groups. Relationships in a group affect the behavior of people, and the internal subjective attitude of a student towards his officer is important in forming a positive attitude towards military service. If, for some reason, this relationship is negative, obedience becomes forced, and the service process becomes boring, resulting in disagreements and disappointments. On the contrary, a positive relationship between an officer-teacher and students makes service easier and turns it into a hobby. This helps to cultivate the necessary fighting qualities in students. Where mutual relations are built on the basis of military regulations, military discipline will always be strong.

Basic concepts: activity, interest, mood, enthusiasm, knowledge, skills, high spirituality.

Enter. The implementation of scientific and technical achievements has created the basis for the rapid development of almost all spheres of human activity. At the same time, the role of professional training of specialists has significantly increased. Based on this, the need to increase the quality of education and its continuous improvement has arisen.

Considering that ensuring the independence and territorial integrity of the state is the main task of the Armed Forces, the problem of training officers and improving the military education system is relevant in all countries of the world.

Since its inception, military education has always attracted the attention of scientists and practitioners, employees of various fields of knowledge, social spheres and government agencies. Many consider military education to be one of the factors influencing the future of the army and the state as a whole, that is, the development of society, global processes, and military development. This attention is due to the fact that military education has always ensured high combat capability and combat readiness of the Armed Forces.

Results and Discussion. Focusing the structure of motives on a practical direction creates an important opportunity and necessary conditions for the emergence of a scientific basis for effective forms of motivational, volitional, moral, emotional, cognitive, regulatory influence on the human personality. The

complexity of the human labor system, the effective implementation of the aspects of moral, spiritual, aesthetic, and spiritual education in production, as well as the influence of radio, television, and propaganda, the stabilization, improvement, and purposefulness of professional training in extreme and stressful situations, all of which contribute to the change in the scope of individual motives.

The sphere of motives of a person is reflected in his needs, volitional qualities and functional capabilities. If we approach it from the history of research on motives, then in this case it is a special type of interpretation of them as spiritual guides of human life and activity. It is emphasized in scientific sources that the concept of motive mainly applies to mammals.

The concept of motives in relation to humans includes all types of instigators and instigators (such as motives, needs, interests, goals, aspirations, motivated attitudes, etc.). Considerations about the flow of human motives provide a unique tactical approach to the analysis of the psychic development of the individual in order to psychologically explain the structure of human motives, their main functional mechanisms, and the problem of developing a strategic plan for directing the formation process.

The activities of officer-teachers are aimed at establishing, strengthening and managing these relationships. The system of educational relationships is constantly being established. For example, these include the redistribution of students in one or another process of educational activity, the definition of responsibilities and the distribution of tasks, the timing and form of reporting, and punishment for shortcomings in service. However, both during and outside the service period, people with will, consciousness and emotions interact with each other. Therefore, it is impossible to completely separate professional relationships from personal relationships, and personal relationships from non-professional relationships. Both during education and in non-educational situations, people with specific feelings, volitional qualities, thinking and worldview enter into relationships with each other. This indicates that the relationships between students have a deep spiritual and emotional content.

As is known, relations within military groups are regulated by general military regulations and moral standards. Mutual respect, combat camaraderie, active participation in public affairs, and the desire to help comrades in any circumstances are characteristic of relations based on military regulations.

The relationship between officers and students is based on such principles as individual leadership, maintaining a certain distance between military

personnel of different ages, mutual respect and the authority of superiors. Unconditional obedience to superiors and commanders does not undermine the personality of a military personnel. Because their interests coincide, they serve the same goal, the defense of the Motherland.

The formation of relationships in a team based on military regulations largely depends on the soldiers' adaptation to the team, their communication methods, and their psychological compatibility. Knowing these indicators, it is possible to manage relationships in the group.

In any form of interaction, various socio-psychological phenomena occur. One of these phenomena is imitation, and its role in the development of the human personality is incomparable, every person imitates someone in life, tries to be like him. In the language of psychologists, one of the sources of social knowledge and experience in humans is imitation.

Another socio-psychological phenomenon that occurs in relationships is competition or rivalry. Competition has a energizing effect on people. It is advisable to use this phenomenon to increase the level of combat and socio-political readiness in groups.

In addition, relations between students are divided into relations between superiors and subordinates, seniors and juniors, as well as relations between equals. The content of such relations is set out in the Disciplinary Regulations of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

It is worth mentioning that willpower plays an important role in overcoming difficulties in reaching a decision and implementing it. In most psychological cases, a person's decision is inextricably linked to the process of internal effort, characterized by seriousness and tension, combined with overcoming the influence of the level of priority of his needs as a necessary measure. Such an attitude (necessity) to overcome contradictions within a person is governed, firstly, by certain desires of the subject, entrenched negative habits; secondly, by a sense of familiarity with life events; thirdly, by the struggle with disapproved moral principles and traditions, which is considered a characteristic feature of a volitional act, which is governed by volitional effort.

Team spirit is a set of emotions that arise in team members in relation to a particular event. Team spirit has a very strong influence and is a motivator for student behavior and activity.

Indeed, some types of team mood (enthusiasm, confidence in success, high spirits) contribute to its success, while others (bad mood, lack of self-confidence,

boredom, resentment, and dissatisfaction) on the contrary reduce the team's capabilities.

In addition, military teams have their own traditions. The phenomenon of preserving some characteristic of a team over time is called tradition.

Conclusions and recommendations. The socio-psychological environment (microenvironment, moral environment) is a complex concept that includes the feelings of each student, the level of satisfaction of their social needs (communication, mutual respect, friendship, the level of manifestation of their abilities, etc.), and the mood of the team. The complex of feelings and experiences that are simultaneously manifested in all or most members of the team is called the mood of the team.

If the mood of an individual depends equally on physiological, psychological and other social factors, then the mood of a group is primarily the result of the entire system of social relations (economic, political, ideological, spiritual). Social life is determined by the material and spiritual conditions of people's lives.

Thus, a positive relationship between an officer-teacher and students makes service easier and turns it into a hobby. This helps to cultivate the necessary fighting qualities in students. Both during training and in extracurricular situations, people with unique feelings, volitional qualities, thinking and worldview enter into relationships with each other. This indicates that the relationships between students have a deep spiritual and emotional content.

Group motivation has a very strong influence on student behavior. The student's internal subjective attitude towards his officer is important in forming a positive attitude towards military service.

List of references used:

1. G'oziyev E.G'. Umumiy psixologiya.-T:Universitet, 2002.-B.137.
2. Raximov F.B. Harbiy psixologiya va pedagogika asoslari Darslik.-B.;Umud, 2022.-151 b.
3. Uzoqov A.M. Harbiy psixologiya va pedagogika O'quv qo'llanma.-B.;Kamolot, 2022.-131 b.
4. Nasriddinov Ch.R. Harbiy psixologiya. O'quv qo'llanma T.;Fan, 2004.-123 b.
5. Nazarov T.T "Ta'lim va innovatsion tadqiqotlar" xalqaro ilmiy metodik jurnal 8-son 274-bet Buxoro 2022-yil.

